

MECHANICAL PROPERTY OF PAPER-THERMOSETTING RESIN COMPOSITE

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1 General Introduction

Recycling and reusing is a noticeable method to reduce trash discharge and to save resource. Recycling paper is one of the most successful cases as it contributes to energy saving, low cost, low wood consumption and environmental protection [1-4]. It was reported that the recycling rate in Europe reached 64.5% in 2007, which confirms that the industry is on the path to meeting its voluntary target of 66% by 2010 [5]. According to the data of Japan Preliminary Report on Paper, Printing, Plastic Products and Rubber Products Statistics, as shows in Fig. 1, the waste paper recovery rate increased year by year. On the other hand, the waste paper reuse rate was not increase with waste paper recovery rate. This situation reveals the wasted paper was accumulated and the paper reusing industry has big development space in Japan.

Paper materials are widely used, such as packing industry, media platform and house and living things. Paper and paperboard are fibrous materials made from chemical and mechanical pulp, like wood and plant straw, in a continuous process. They are built from cellulose fibers jointed by hydrogen bonds and some additional elements like talc. They can be produced into many kinds of structure according to different requirement, such as paper tube, corrugated paperboard, normal paperboard, and so on.

However, its low mechanical property limits possible applications. Due to the non-homogenous and anisotropic nature of the paper materials, it is difficult to predict accurately the materials responses. Therefore, they exhibit complex mechanical behavior, commonly characterized by a highly anisotropic linear elastic response (under moderate mechanical loading) and no-linear response (attributed to plastic response) under high load [6].

Many researchers have paid attention to paper materials.

The mechanical and physical properties of single layer particleboards made with various ratios of waste paperboard fibers to wood particles was investigated by Amir Eshraghi and Habibollah Khademieslam [8]. Urea formaldehyde resin was also used as adhesive in different amounts of 9% and 10%. Static bending strength, internal bonding and thickness swelling were measure during the study. The results revealed with increasing waste paperboard fiber content up to 50%, the modulus of rupture and modulus of elasticity of the panels increased. However, further additions decreased both of the values. The internal bonding property was found decreased with the addition of waste paperboard fiber in all panel types. All the physical and mechanical property improved by increasing the amount urea formaldehyde resin.

In order to describe the mechanical behavior of paperboard, several material models had been proposed. In the study of Qingxi Xia, etc. [8], a three-dimensional constitutive model of the anisotropic elastic-plastic behavior of paper and paperboard is proposed. The initial elastic behavior is modelled to be linear and orthotropic. The onset of plastic flow is captured by a non-quadratic yield surface. The yield surface is taken to evolve anisotropically with a scalar measure of plastic strain, with plastic flow modelled using an associated flow rule. It was found the numerical results have a good agreement with experimental data. The model can be applied to simulate a wide range of in-plane problems for paper and paperboard such as the behavior under bending or inhomogeneous, multiaxial in-plane loading. The accurate also can be improved if more experimental information could be provided.

Science the water content has a significant effect on mechanical property on paper materials, Navaranjan, etc. evaluated the humidity effect on the elastic property and failure mechanism of two types of layered corrugated paperboard structures composed of entirely recycled material and virgin radiate pine kraft and mixed fiber linerboards and fluting medium. The compression tests were conducted under constant relative humidity environment from 50% to 90%. The fracture behavior was also observed through confocal laser scanning microscope. It was found water absorption potential in components made of virgin fiber is greater than that of components composed of recycled fibers [9]. The carbon fiber reinforced paper-based friction (CFRPF) material was prepared by paper-making process. The effect of the cashew-modified phenolic resin on the mechanical, thermal and tribological behavior of CFRPF was examined by Fei and He Jun. It was found the hardness and tensile strength increased with the increase of resin content. Scanning electron microscope (SEM) observation results indicated the microvoids were decreased with the increase of resin content which enhanced mechanical property of the materials [10]. In this study, the mechanical property of paperboard composite was investigated. Three types of unsaturated polyester resin were used to improve properties of recycled paperboard. The resin can help not only to improve the resistance to water but also to enhance the mechanical property. Tensile test was conducted on both unnotched specimen and notched specimens. The reductions were compared between different types of materials. To investigate the shear performance, short beam bending test was conducted both in different angel of 3-type paperboard composite. Optical microscope and SEM was employed to observe the materials and fracture area respectively. Voids and combination between fiber and matrix were compared to analyze the improvement effects from resin.

2 Materials and Experiment

2.1 Paperboard

Paperboard is in general composed of several pulp fiber sheets bonded by starch or adhesive material, and is usually a multi-layered structure. The

paperboard used in this research is illustrated in Fig. 2.

Due to the fabrication process, the properties of paperboard express obviously anisotropy. The machine rolling direction was defined as MD and the cross or transverse direction was defined as CD. The designed thickness of the paperboard is 1 mm.

2.2 Matrix

Recycled paperboard (DAIWA ITAGAMI CO. LTD.) was used as reinforcement with a density of 685 g/m². Three kinds of unsaturated polyester resin with different flexibility (Highest flexibility to lowest: Showa Denko K. K.: FKS-4000, 150HRBQNTNW and LP-1BQM) were used as matrix. (Polymer was mixed with the hardener MEKPO (PERMEK N; NOF Corporation) in a ratio of 100:0.7). The properties of matrix and ratio of weight content of paperboard composite are listed in Table 1 and Table 2. The composite plate was fabricated by hand lay-up method. After fabrication, the materials were disposed on steel moulds in 24 hours for cure. Post cure was followed in the condition of 100 °C maintained 2 hours.

2.3 Specimens preparation

After fabrication, the plates were cut into unnotched and notched specimens. The width of unnotched specimens and notched specimens were 20 mm and 30 mm respectively. After cutting the specimens, 10 mm hole were drilled in the geometric center of the specimens with drills from H.A.M. PRECISION TOOLS (Type: 342) at the speed of 2300 rad/min.

2.4 Tensile Test

Tensile test were performed by using an Instron universal testing machine under a speed of 1 mm/min. For the specimen with a hole, the notched strength was calculated. Additionally, strain gage (KYOWA KFG-10-120-C1-11) was used to measure the strain during testing process.

The unnotched strength and notched strength of specimen with holes can be calculated by the equation (1) and (2).

$$\sigma = \frac{F_{\max}}{wh} \quad (1)$$

$$\sigma_n = \frac{F_{\max}}{(w-d)h} \quad (2)$$

where σ_n is notched strength of specimen with holes, w is the width of the specimen, d is the diameter of the hole, h is the thickness and F_{\max} is the max load during tensile test.

2.5 Short Beam Bending

For 3-point bending, was conducted according to JIS K7057. The specimens were cut into 10 mm and 20 mm in width and length respectively. The machine used in tensile test was also used in here with speed of 1 mm/min. The span distance is 50 mm. According to mechanics of materials the stress of specimens can calculate by the following equation.

$$\tau = \frac{3FL}{2bh^2} \quad (3)$$

where τ is the shear strength of the specimen, F is the load, L is the span distance, b is the width and h is the thickness. The size of specimens and machine used in the test is shown in Fig.3.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Mechanical properties of paperboard

In order to investigate the anisotropic property of paperboard materials, tensile test was conducted on both direction, included MD and CD. The stress-strain curve is shown in Fig. 4. The strength and modulus in MD were 34.1 MPa and 4.4 GPa respectively and in CD were 17.4 MPa and 1.9 GPa respectively. The value in CD were around half of MD. This mainly caused by fabrication process of paperboard in which most of the fibers were distributed in MD.

3.2 Tensile property

Tensile test was conducted on 4-type materials. Paper type represented original recycled paperboard materials. FKS-4000, 150HR and LP-1 types represented different composite made of corresponding resin. The tensile process is shown in Fig. 5. From the stress-strain curve, it was found strength was increased after combining with resin. However, the elongation was decreased in 150HR type. The fractured specimens are shown in Fig. 6. For unnotched specimens of FKS-4000 type shows delamination between different plies of paperboard. But for others, it was difficult to find obvious delamination

The modulus of tensile test is shown in Fig. 7. The specimens were all taken from MD of paperboard composite. The results indicated the modulus in 150HR type specimens hold highest modulus although the modulus of LP-1 resin is the highest. It was considered the modulus has a strong relation with impregnation during fabrication process of paperboard composite. From the results of tensile test in Fig. 8, the strength was increased after combining with resin. Although the strength of paperboard and the pure resin were lower, the improvement was remarkable. The strength reached 61.13 MPa, 69.63 MPa and 87.56 MPa in FKS-4000, 150HR and LP-1 type respectively. It was considered the resin made up the defect of voids in paperboard materials and provided better deliver of stress in the materials.

On the other hand, the notched strength was also increased after combining with resin. However, the decreasing ratio became bigger. For example, in the case of LP-1, the decreasing ratio was 44.1%, which means the LP-1 held highest sensitivity to hole. Compared with the three types, the notched strength was very close.

3.3 Short beam bending property

Different fractures from different type of paperboard composite after short beam bending test are shown in Fig.9. Both 150HR and LP-1 specimens show tensile fracture after short beam bending test. However, the delamination could be obviously found in FKS-4000 type specimens. The results show the 150HR and LP-1 specimens held similar resistance to shearing both in MD and CD. The shear strength in CD was around 70% of MD according to formula 3. Compared to 150HR and LP-1, FKS-4000 was weaker in this aspect.

3.4 Optical observation

To investigate the impregnation between fiber and matrix, optical observation was conduct on undamaged materials. The results are shown in Fig. 11. The observation was taken under 100 times, 250 times and 1000 times of 3 types of paperboard composite. In order to evaluate the ratio of voids or little impregnation area in the materials, ImageJ software was employed. The main process is illustrated in Fig. 12. The first picture shows the original observed picture. It will finally convert to picture 4 and the black area was chosen as voids or

little impregnation area. This content was 25.5%, 11.8% and 16.9% for FKS-400, 150HR and LP-1 respectively. From the result, it was revealed the FKS-4000 had the highest voids or little impregnation which caused it low shear resistance property. Compared with LP-1, 150HR had lower voids or little impregnation which was considered as the main reason provided 150HR higher modulus in tensile test.

3.5 SEM observation

SEM observation was also conducted to examine the combination between fiber and matrix on the fracture surface of failure specimens. The observation results are shown in Fig.13. From the observation, good connection between fiber and matrix could be found in 3 types of paperboard composite. However the matrix was relatively insufficient which affects the mechanical property seriously. To improve the impregnation condition would be a better choice to perfect paperboard composite.

4. Conclusion

In this study, mechanical property of paperboard composite was investigated with different type of unsaturated polyester resin. The follow conclusion was obtained.

1. The modulus and strength was increased after combining with resin. Compared with FKS-4000 and 150HR, LP-1 was gained the highest strength but also the highest sensitivity to open hole.

2. From short beam bending test, it was found that the FKS-4000 specimens had the lowest interlaminar property and easy to happen delamination. From the optical observation, it was found that the voids or the little resin area were the main factor contributed to its lower interlaminar property.

3. According to the SEM observation, it was indicated that the combination between fiber and matrix was good in the 3 type of specimens. Therefore, the voids were considered the most important factor to improve the mechanical property of paperboard composite.

Further work will put the emphasis on the effect of resin content on mechanical property of paperboard composite.

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Table

Table.1 Mechanical property of different matrix

Resin	Density g/cm ³	Strength MPa	Modulus GPa	Elongation %
Fks-4000	1.25	8.20	0.09	5.45
150HR	1.19	42.00	3.20	2.18
LP-1	1.12	61.34	3.27	2.37

Table.2 Fiber content of paperboard composite

Type	Number of Ply	Gram Weight g/m ²	Weight Ratio %
Paper	1	715	/
Fks-4000	2	2298	62.2
150HR	2	2654	53.9
LP-1	2	2408	59.4

Figure

Fig.1. A wastepaper recovery and availability in Japan

Fig.3. Short beam bending test and specimen dimension

Fig.2. Paperboard used in the research

Fig.4. Stress-strain curve of paperboard

Fig.5. Stress-stain curve of paperboard composite

Fig.6. Failure specimen of tensile test

Fig.7. Modulus comparison of tensile test

Fig.8. Strength comparison of tensile test

Fig.9. Specimens of short beam bending test

Fig.10. Comparison of shear strength

a. Optical observation of FKS-4000 specimen

b. Optical observation of 150HR specimen

c. Optical observation of LP-1 specimen

Fig.11. Optical observation of undamaged specimens

Fig.12. Main process of ImageJ calculation

b. SEM observation of fracture surface of 150HR

a. SEM observation of fracture surface of FKS-4000

c. SEM observation of fracture surface of LP-1
Fig.13. SEM observation of paperboard composite